

RADIOBLOCKS

Project ID: 101093934

Report on Modular PAF Processing Architecture

Deliverable:	Milestone 22
Lead beneficiary:	MPG
Submission date:	01.09.25
Dissemination level:	Public

Version: A

Status: Released

Date: 04.08.25

Table of Contents

Table of Contents.....	1
List of acronyms.....	2
General.....	3
Scope.....	3
Task description.....	3
Introduction.....	4
Background.....	4
The EDD Backend System.....	5
Overview.....	5
Design.....	6
Capabilities.....	6
CI/CD and packaging.....	7
Dadaflow.....	8
Strong typing.....	9
DAG processing.....	10
Conclusion.....	12

List of acronyms

AD	Applicable Document
CI/CD	Continuous integration / continuous deployment
COTS	Commercial Off-the-Shelf
DAG	Directed Acyclic Graph
EDD	Effelsberg Direct Digitization
FPGA	Field Programmable Gate Array
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
MPCDF	Max Planck Computing and Data Facility
MPIfR	Max Planck Institute for Radio Astronomy
PAF	Phased Array Feed
RFI	Radio Frequency Interference
RD	Reference Document
TCC	Tensor Core Correlator
VLBI	Very Long Baseline Interferometry
WP	Work Package

General

Scope

This report covers work conducted as part of Task 5.5 of RADIOBLOCKS WP5. The scope is limited to the systems and software development conducted in the course of preparing for RADIOBLOCKS deliverable D5.7 (“Software/firmware repositories containing developed code and documentation”).

Task description

As described in WP3 the development and deployment of the next generation of cryogenic Phased Array Feeds (PAFs) onto telescopes at multiple existing and new RIs will transform scientific capabilities. However, it will also provide a step-change in the size and complexity of their data outputs, which will require the development of new high performance backend processing capabilities. Currently deployed PAFs, such as those used by RIs as the SKA pathfinder and precursor facilities APERTIF and ASKAP have custom backend solutions to support beamforming and correlation. Whilst these address the needs of the specific facilities, they do not provide a common, efficient, nor open-source solution that can be easily reused by other facilities.

Task 5.5 will address this by the development of a general PAF backend solution based on commercial-off-the shelf (COTS) hardware. The design goal is to produce a modular and scalable real time PAF backend processing solution, encompassing modules for PAF beamforming and the production of typical radio astronomical data products (e.g. full-Stokes spectra, pulsar timing and search data). Such a backend will be capable of supporting a wide array of PAF designs at various RIs through scaling of hardware for different numbers of elements and receiver bandwidths. This task will support and work in tandem with the development of next generation PAF technologies in WP3 and 4.

Introduction

Task 5.5 of RADIOBLOCKS WP 5 focuses on developing a modular processing toolkit to meet the high data-rate and complex processing demands of modern Phased Array Feed (PAF) receivers. This effort has progressed substantially, producing two major developments:

- The Effelsberg Direct Digitisation (EDD) backend system
- The Dadaflow C++20/CUDA library

Here, we present the current status of these systems and describe how they address the requirements of Task 5.5.

Background

PAFs expand the field of view of radio telescopes by fully sampling the electric field at the focal plane, enabling electronic beam steering. This allows the formation of multiple beams, each with a solid angle similar to the primary beam.

Implementing beamforming in software requires digitising signals from all PAF elements and distributing them across sufficient hardware before summing with appropriate complex weights. Developing a modular toolkit capable of this entails addressing the following challenges:

Data transport: A typical PAF has on the order of 100 elements with bandwidths ≥ 1 GHz, producing aggregate data rates exceeding 1 Tb/s, comparable to those of large interferometric arrays.

Orchestration: High data rates necessitate distributed hardware for beamforming and correlation. Processing must be coordinated across all participating nodes, with continuous monitoring and accessible status information for both users and automated alerting systems.

Performance: To reduce hardware requirements, processing software and firmware must exploit hardware acceleration efficiently.

Functionality: Although Task 5.5 does not explicitly cover downstream beam processing, a complete toolkit should also support standard radio astronomy modes, including continuum spectroscopy, VLBI, polarimetry, pulsar search, and pulsar timing.

In addition to these domain-specific challenges, the toolkit must meet general software engineering standards for reliability, usability, and extensibility.

To meet these requirements, the Task 5.5 team has developed:

1. The Effelsberg Direct Digitisation (EDD) backend system — a general-purpose orchestration and management framework for radio astronomy backends.
2. Dadaflow — a modern, low-level directed acyclic graph (DAG) pipelining framework built with C++20 and CUDA.

The EDD Backend System

Originally conceived as the development framework for next-generation Effelsberg backends, the EDD system has been significantly re-engineered to meet RADIOBLOCKS Task 5.5 objectives.

Overview

The EDD backend system consists of a suite of software and configuration repositories that provide the information and tools necessary to deploy, operate and monitor radioastronomy backends on COTS computer clusters. Augmenting these repositories are an ecosystem of plugins that extend the EDD backend by providing functionality in the form of support for new observing modes, communication protocols or hardware. Figure 1 provides a high-level overview of the tools, technologies and capabilities that compose the EDD backend system. Below we discuss these in detail.

Figure 1: The EDD backend system which implements the modular PAF processing toolkit. Blue shows capabilities, orange shows technologies and green shows tooling.

Design

The EDD backend relies on several core concepts/technologies. These are detailed below.

Modular design: The EDD backend system is composed of a common core software stack that is deployed at all participating telescope sites, and a suite of selectable plug-in modules which are deployed based on the specific needs of that site.

Commodity hardware: For reasons of cost, replaceability, upgradability, support, and maintenance, the EDD targets COTS hardware wherever possible.

Any-to-any data routing: To remain flexible and enable the development of complex processing chains that support multiple science programs simultaneously, the EDD relies on any-to-any data routing via multicast Ethernet. For performance reasons, we typically use L2 multicast networks and rely on the software packages SPEAD2, which provides support for high-performance SPEAD-protocol data acquisition and transmission, and mkrecv/mksend, which provides runtime-configurable interfacing between the SPEAD2 library and the PSRDADA shared memory ring buffer library.

High-speed networking: As necessitated by the high data rates of receivers such as PAFs, the EDD backend system relies on high-speed 100-GbE+ networking, targeting between 200 and 400 Gb/s of network I/O per computing node.

Virtualisation: To decouple the EDD backend from the hardware it is deployed on, we rely on virtualisation via containerisation. This allows for isolation of resources on the host system and simpler lifetime management and fault tolerance for processing pipelines. On larger backend deployments, we also fully virtualise the underlying cluster hardware using virtual machines. Critically, when combined with the CI/CD and packaging used in the EDD, virtualisation ensures pipeline reproducibility.

Networked storage: Real observations require recording of processed data products. To satisfy this need, we make use of high-capacity, high-throughput distributed file systems connected over high-speed Infiniband or Ethernet networks.

Capabilities

The EDD backend system supports (or will support, once current developments are complete) the following observing modes:

Continuum spectroscopy and polarimetry: A high-resolution spectrometer is included as part of the EDD core software. It supports dual polarisation (XX, YY) and full-Stokes (S0, S1, S2, S3) modes, and performs noise diode gating to produce spectra both with and without

the noise diode active. The spectrometer can generate 32 million channels and offers “zoom bands” for reduced data rates.

Pulsar folding, search, and baseband recording: A general-purpose pulsar pipeline, currently being migrated from the EDD core to a plugin, supports coherently dedispersed pulsar folding and the generation of high-time-resolution, full-polarisation, coherently dedispersed dynamic spectra for pulsar searches. It also provides baseband voltage recording, with the maximum recording bandwidth limited only by the write speed of the distributed file system.

VLBI: A dedicated plugin developed under RADIOBLOCKS Task 5.5 provides the same core functions as the widely used Digital Baseband Converter (DBBC) instruments, including digital down-conversion, rescaling, and packing into VDIF format. It has been successfully deployed in VLBI observations with telescopes in Germany, Italy, South Africa, Thailand, China, and Australia, and was used at the Thai National Radio Telescope to conduct the country’s first-ever VLBI observation.

Real-time transient search: Added in late 2024, this plugin enables real-time fast transient searches using CPU-only processing. It relies on the high-performance dedispersion and template-matching algorithms from the TransientX software. The plugin is currently in commissioning but is expected to become generally available this year.

Correlation and beamforming: The principal development for RADIOBLOCKS Task 5.5 is an interferometer and PAF processing plugin implementing correlation, beamforming, and PAF calibration routines. It builds on work from RADIOBLOCKS WP 4 by wrapping the Tensor Core Correlator (TCC) library to deliver an orchestrated, high-performance correlator. This is paired with a state-of-the-art beamformer that leverages Tensor-core-enabled GPUs, supporting both subarray beamforming, where different antenna subsets are beamformed simultaneously, and “incoherent beam subtraction,” a technique pioneered in the visibility domain at the GMRT and later refined on the MeerKAT telescope. In this mode, incoherent beams (sum of antenna powers) for all subarrays are generated and subtracted from the coherent beams, effectively eliminating autocorrelations and significantly reducing RFI. This plugin will first be deployed on the ARGOS prototype telescope in Crete before being used with the Effelsberg CryoPAF receiver.

CI/CD and packaging

To meet the goals of Task 5.5 it is not sufficient that the EDD backend system be modular. The system must also be easy to use and straightforward to integrate at observing sites. To address this, we have streamlined our build and deployment processes, taking full ownership of packaging and dependency management. This has been achieved through

three key mechanisms: Debian packaging, publicly accessible container image registries and robust CI/CD pipelines

Whenever code is pushed to any repository related to the EDD system, the software is automatically built, tested, and packaged. Resulting Debian packages are then published to an Aptly repository hosted at the MPIfR.

For the EDD core repository, responsible for orchestration and operation of processing pipelines and services, Docker image builds are triggered upon each push. These builds fetch dependencies from the Aptly repository, enabling fast and lightweight image creation. The resulting images are published to a public container registry hosted by the Max Planck Computing and Data Facility (MPCDF) in Garching.

To deploy the EDD at a telescope site, only a single Ansible configuration file is needed. This file specifies the site's hardware and the required plugins. Using a common EDD deployment playbook, this configuration enables fully automated deployment, pulling all necessary software and firmware from the remote container registry.

The impact of these changes has been significant. What previously took half a day to build now takes approximately 20 minutes. This improvement has accelerated our development cycle and substantially simplified site deployments, as partner sites no longer need to build the system themselves.

The ultimate goal of this initiative is to ensure reliable, robust versioning of the entire EDD system, enabling bit-level reproducibility of processing pipelines. As a final step, we are working toward snapshotting the Aptly repository, which will allow complete versioning and rollback of the EDD system and its dependencies, creating the equivalent of an “EDD Debian distribution.”

Dadaflow

Significant software development took place last year under the COMPACT ERC project (grant number 101078094), including the implementation of an offline, coherently dedispersing beamformer leveraging modern C++20 features. During this development cycle, we identified that several capabilities introduced in C++20 could enable the creation of a compile-time, strongly typed Directed Acyclic Graph (DAG) processing library for general-purpose data workflows.

This insight led to the development of the dadaflow library, a new framework focused on the needs of high-performance radio astronomy data processing. In particular, DADAFLOW introduces composable, compile-time-generated, multi-dimensional data types designed to represent common structures in radio telescope outputs, especially from PAFs.

These types carry all necessary metadata to fully describe each dimension, enabling the creation of processors that accept and return well-defined, strongly typed data. These processors can be composed into processing graphs that are validated at compile time, ensuring correctness and efficiency.

Dadaflow has become the de facto framework for high-performance software within the EDD backend. It currently underpins the VLBI, interferometry and transient search plugins within the backend and is being used beyond the EDD to implement high-performance spectrometers for EMI measurement systems.

As a brief introduction to the library, we below introduce some two key features of dadaflow.

Strong typing

A common problem in radio astronomy processing (in particular with array processing) is the need to handle multidimensional data sets and track their metadata. In dadaflow this problem is solved with the DescribedData class:

```
template <typename ContainerType, typename... Dimensions>
class DescribedData;
```

This generic template base allows users to compose multidimensional strongly typed data types. For example:

```
using TAFTPData = DescribedData<
    thrust::device_vector<char2>,
    TimeDimensionN<0>,
    AntennaDimension,
    FrequencyDimension,
    TimeDimensionN<1>,
    PolarisationDimension
>;
TAFTPData taftp;
```

Here we are creating a 5-dimensional data type with dimensions of time, antenna, frequency, time and polarisation (from outer/slowest to inner/fastest). The storage class for the instance is here defined to be a thrust vector using GPU memory, but can be any class that implements the C++ STL container interface. These data types are simple to construct and use and carry all relevant metadata for each of their dimensions, e.g.

```
taftp.resize({10, 64, 128, 256, 2}); // Resize the instance
std::cout << taftp.TimeDimensionN<0>::nsamples(); // Outputs "10"
```

```

std::cout << taftp.nantennas(); // Outputs "64"
std::cout << taftp.nchannels(); // Outputs "128"
std::cout << taftp.TimeDimensionN<1>::nsamples(); // Outputs "256"
std::cout << taftp.npolarisations(); // Outputs "2"

// Specify that the inner dimension has 1 us sampling
taftp.TimeDimensionN<1>::timestep(
    std::chrono::duration<long double, pico>(1e6));

```

The use of such types simplifies the building of complex processing workflows as data are fully self-describing.

DAG processing

The second major component of dadaflow is its directed acyclic graph processing engine. This allows developers to build asynchronous processing pipelines that are well suited to high-performance batch processing. The dadaflow DAG engine relies on some key concepts:

- **Shared pointers:** Objects passed between processes in the graph should be wrapped in shared pointers. These pointers must be passed between processes and queues by value to assure copy/move semantics.
- **Memory management:** All processes are responsible for allocating the memory needed to store their outputs.
- **Concurrency:** All processes in the graph are asynchronous and run in their own dedicated thread.
- **Back pressure:** To avoid excess memory allocation we use back pressure to impose limits on what can be produced by upstream components in the graph. This is done through two methods: 1.) restricted resource pools which prevent a processes from over allocating output buffers and 2.) finite queue depths which cause upstream processes to block if downstream processes cannot clear their queues.
- **Metadata completeness:** All processes are responsible for ensuring that any metadata they receive on their inputs is, where appropriate, forwarded to their outputs with any changes based on the algorithms run in the process.
- **Single consumer, single producer:** All queues in the graph are pushed to by only one process and read from by only one process. Merging or splitting queues is performed via aggregating or multiplexing.

The nodes of the DAG can be any callable object (e.g. function, functor, lambda, etc.) and type traits are used to determine the object's properties at compile time. When all nodes are added to the graph and the connections between nodes are specified, the user can run the graph asynchronously, with dadaflow taking care to provide controlled graph shutdown mechanisms. A toy SAXPY example of a dadaflow graph is shown below:

```

using Vec      = std::vector<float>;
using VecPtr   = std::shared_ptr<Vec>;

Graph graph;

// add_node signature is (callable, name)
auto& x_array_source = graph.add_node(
    []() -> VecPtr {
        return std::make_shared<Vec>(10, 1);
    },
    "x-source"
);

auto& y_array_source = graph.add_node(
    []() -> VecPtr {
        return std::make_shared<Vec>(10, 1);
    },
    "y-source"
);

float constant = 123.456f;
auto& saxpy = graph.add_node(
    [](VecPtr xptr, VecPtr const& yptr) -> VecPtr {
        auto& x = xptr.get();
        auto const& y = yptr.get();
        for (int ii = 0; ii < x.size(); ++ii){
            x[ii] = x[ii] * constant + y[ii];
        }
        return xptr;
    },
    "saxpy"
);

auto& display = graph.add_node(
    [](VecPtr const& xptr) -> void {
        auto const& x = xptr.get();
        for (auto const& val: x){

```

```

        std::cout << val << "\n";
    }
},
"display
"
);

// bind output 0 of x_array_source to saxpy input 0
graph.connect<0,0>(x_array_source, saxpy, "x->saxpy", 3);
// bind output 0 of y_array_source to saxpy input 1
graph.connect<0,1>(y_array_source, saxpy, "y->saxpy", 3);
// bind output 0 of saxpy to display input 0
graph.connect<0,0>(saxpy, display, "saxpy->display", 3);

// Validate the graph and prepare for execution
graph.prepare();

graph.run_async(); // start execution
std::this_thread::sleep_for(10s); // run for 10 seconds
graph.stop(); // start the shutdown process for the graph
graph.await(); // block until the graph has come to a stop

```

The dadaflow library is currently a part of the psrdada_cpp library maintained by the MPIfR (https://gitlab.mpcdf.mpg.de/mpifr-bdg/psrdada_cpp).

Conclusion

Since the start of the project important progress has been made. This is demonstrated through improved modularity and a complete overhaul of the deployment system for the EDD backend resulting in a massive reduction in deployment time, and the construction of an asynchronous high-performance DAG-based data processing pipeline framework. With these in place we do not foresee problems meeting the goals set for Deliverable D5.7 by month 48 of the project.